

Effects of environmental variability on population dynamics of golden carpet shell clam (*Polititapes aureus*)

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Abstract

The population dynamics of the golden carpet shell clam *Polititapes aureus* (Gmelin, 1791) were studied over the course of six years in the ria of Arousa (Galicia, NW Spain). Density reached a value of 62.29 individuals m⁻² and biomass was 76.30 g m⁻². Recruitment was related to water temperature, to food availability measured as fluorescence and to density-dependent phenomena starting at 39 individuals m⁻². The condition factor and mortality showed a clear annual periodicity, while growth rate G₃₀ was biannual. Growth was fitted to a seasonal von Bertalanffy function, with L_∞ = 43.6 mm; K = 0.360 y⁻¹; C = 0.65 and t_s = 1.21, with a confidence interval determined by bootstrapping. The instantaneous mortality rate for individuals aged 1 and 2 years was 0.94 in spring-summer and 0.14 in autumn-winter. The fishing mortality rate had little effect on the population. A model was built to explain the natural mortality rate as function of temperature, salinity, fluorescence, and the condition factor. The results allow the application of fishery management tools based on their population dynamics and to measure their effectiveness considering the environmental variability. They also show the vulnerability of these stocks to changes resulting from climate change.

Keywords: abiotic factors, biotic factors, environmental variability, population dynamics, mortality, seasonal growth

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1. Introduction

Originally described as *Venus aurea* (Gmelin, 1791), the golden carpet shell, *Polititapes aureus* (Gmelin, 1971), has undergone numerous changes in the taxonomic nomenclature. Two of the most widespread names were *Venerupis aurea* (Gmelin, 1791) and *Paphia aurea* (Gmelin, 1791) which are no longer accepted [1]. This clam lives on gravel, muddy gravel, and soft black mud bottoms up to 30 m deep in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean from Norway to Morocco, the Mediterranean Sea, and the Black Sea.

Polititapes aureus is a species of commercial interest usually caught together with other commercial species such as the pullet carpet shell, *Venerupis corrugata* (Gmelin, 1791) and the banded carpet shell, *Polititapes rhomboides* (Pennant, 1777). The annual average harvest of these species in Galicia (NW Spain) was over 13,119 kg with a mean value of 4.57 € kg⁻¹ from 2001 to 2022 (www.pescadegalicia.com). Spain, Portugal, Ireland, and France are the areas with the highest production rates [2], and it is an appreciate species in Egypt also [3]. In Galicia, the harvesting of these species is regulated under annual management plans

designed by the shellfishers and approved by the administration provided that the proposals comply with the regulations in force [4]. To design management plans, it is necessary to have independent catch information such as data on population dynamics and stock abundance which support regulations based on quota systems and minimum sizes [5].

Polititapes aureus has been the object of stock assessment studies in Galicia (data partially included in this study), France [6–8], and Italy [9]. However, very few studies exist on the population dynamics of this species [10], or the results have not been widely disseminated [11]. In cases like these, management plans are based on stock assessments and catches [4]. While this type of adaptive management is relatively effective if carried out in a continuous manner, the availability of data on population dynamics allows management plans to be adapted to the biology of the species. However, population dynamics are influenced by both genetics and environment [12–14]. Furthermore, in recent decades, there has been increasing interest in understanding the effects of environmental variables on the population dynamics of

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bivalve mollusks, not only because of the interest in harvesting or culture, but also because of the need to understand the implications of climate change. However, long-term studies are required to include environmental variability.

From 2005 to 2011, the Consellería do Mar (The Regional Ministry for the Sea) (Xunta de Galicia) financed a project to standardize procedures for scientific assessment in the management of shellfish beds. The long duration of the project has made it possible to collect a data series with an appropriate length of time to be able to study population dynamics considering interannual variability. The objectives of this study were (i) to gather information on the population dynamics of *P. aureus*, over the course of six years and (ii) to relate it to the environmental variables that may be able to explain variability.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Origin of the data

In the shellfish bed of O Bohído (Figure 1), two strata can be distinguished. In the northern strata, with an area of 143.19 ha and a depth of 1–2 m, the sediments consist of gravel and coarse sand, with the most abundant clam species being *P. aureus*, the rayed artemis, *Dosinia exoleta* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *V. corrugata*, followed by the checkered carpet shell, *Venerupis decussata* (Linnaeus, 1758), and the Japanese carpet shell *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Adams & Reeve, 1850). The southern strata, with an area of 291 ha, is deeper (2–6 m) and has sediment types that range from gravels to mud. The most abundant species are *D. exoleta*, *P. aureus*, and *V. corrugata*.

Figure 1 • Study area. The polygons delimit the sampling strata for stock assessment. The sampling station of the oceanographic variables (triangle), the confinement cages (square), and the floating platform to monitor catches (circle) are indicated. Coordinates in UTM WGS84.

The Technological Institute for the Control of the Marine Environment in Galicia (INTECMAR) records the oceanographic conditions to the North of the bed (Figure 1) weekly and includes the values in three depth ranges, 0–5, 5–10, and 10–15 m (data available at <http://www.intecmar.org>, and Pazos González et al. [15], Morono Mariño et al. [16], and Doval González et al. [17]). In this study, the surface data (0–5 m) for temperature (T , °C), salinity (S), and fluorescence (F , Chl a $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), the last one as an

indicator of food availability, have been used. The average value of the four monthly recordings was considered to be the representative value of each month.

Stocks were assessed by designing a regular stratified sampling program [18] with 34 stations in the northern strata of the bed and 35 in the southern area (Figure 1). Samplings were carried out twice a year from 2006 to 2011, between the last week of April and the first week of May (at the end of each shellfish harvesting campaign) and between the last week of August and the first week of September (before the start of each shellfish harvesting campaign). Two samples were collected from each station using a box corer (0.232 m²) and sieved in situ over 5 mm mesh. The specimens caught were measured to determine the stock in terms of the density (individuals m⁻²; ind m⁻²) of each size class. To calculate the stock in terms of the biomass (g m⁻²) of each size class, size–weight regressions were used (see below). The calculations followed the procedure for populations with a contiguous distribution [19] implemented in ARouSA (<http://arousa.bnmarina.com>). A modal progression study was carried out with the size frequencies using the methods of Bhattacharya and NORMSEP implemented in FISAT-II [20]. Log regressions were used to compare the temporal pattern of recruitment with (i) environmental variables, (ii) condition factor, and (iii) growth and mortality rates (see below).

From February 2006 to October 2011, the population was monitored using six confinement boxes measuring 50 × 40 × 20 cm (length, width, height) placed at depths of 2.5 m (Figure 1). They were filled with sand and covered with 1 cm mesh nets. Each cage contained a group of 25 numbered clams (125 ind m⁻²) measuring over 20 mm in length. The groups of clams from five of the six cages were replaced every month to study mortality rates, while the sixth group was replaced every two months to study growth. Another monthly sampling of 30 individuals was used to determine the size–weight relationship.

The size–weight relationships were estimated by the linear regression (log transformed) of the fresh weight (g) and maximum length (mm) of (i) a subsample of more than 100 individuals from the stock assessments to calculate the stock in terms of biomass and fishing mortality and (ii) 30 specimens before being confined to cages to calculate the monthly condition factor (CF). The CF was estimated as

$$CF = W_m / W_p$$

where W_m is the mean monthly weight of specimens measuring 30 mm and W_p is the estimated weight of individuals of the same size based on the pooled regression of the data obtained during the 72-month study [21].

2.2. Growth and mortality

The study of growth was based on two sets of data: (i) one derived from the modal progression of the cohorts identified in the stock assessments and (ii) the other from confined specimens. By means of the Appeldoorn method (implemented in FISAT-II), the modal progression data were used to obtain the values of constants L_∞ , K , C , and WP of the seasonal growth function (VBGF-E) defined by Somers on the basis of the von Bertalanffy growth function (VBGF) as follows:

$$L_t = L_\infty \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[-K(t - t_0) - S(t) + S(t_0) \right] \right\}$$

$$S(t) = (CK / 2\pi) \sin(2\pi(t - t_s))$$

$$S(t_o) = (CK / 2\pi) \sin(2\pi(t_o - t_s))$$

$$t_s = WP - 0.5$$

where L_t is the expected length at age t , L_∞ is the model asymptotic length, K is a measure of the exponential rate of approach to L_∞ , and t_0 is the theoretical age at which the average length would be zero. C modulates the amplitude of the growth oscillations. For $C = 0$, there is no seasonal oscillation and the model becomes original VBGF. For $C = 1$, growth completely stops once a year at the “winter-point” (WP) [22]. As seed values of L_∞ and K in the Appledoorn method, the values obtained by the Powell-Wetherall and ELEFAN methods (implemented in FISAT-II), respectively, were used.

The data collected from the confinement cages provided the VBGF-E parameters by means of Fabens’ method modified by Francis [23]. To obtain a confidence interval for each parameter of the VBGF-E, the original data were bootstrapped to generate 5,000 new estimates of the VBGF-E. To avoid the effect of any bias on the distribution of the new estimates, a calculation was made for the bias-corrected bootstrap confidence interval with bootstrap percentiles adjusted based on the proportion of bootstrap estimates less than the original estimate [24]. This procedure makes it possible to compare the VBGF-E of the caged individuals with the VBGF-E and the modal sizes obtained in the stock assessments, according to the overlap in the confidence intervals [25].

The instantaneous growth rate G_{30} was also obtained from the confined specimens:

$$G_{30} = \left[\ln(L_2) - \ln(L_1) \right] \cdot 30 / (t_2 - t_1)$$

where L_1 and L_2 are the lengths on days t_1 and t_2 , respectively.

The instantaneous mortality rate of the population (Z_p) was estimated using the age-structured catch curve [20] with density values of the cohorts identified in consecutive samplings so that

$$\ln(N_2) = -Z_p \cdot t + \ln(N_1)$$

where N is the cohort density in consecutive samplings and Z_p is the slope of the regression between $\ln(N_2)$ and the number of days between samplings (t). Z_p was fitted to monthly rates (Z_{p30}) multiplying it by 30 and dividing it by t . Z_{p30} was calculated for individuals from ages 0 to 1 and from 1 to 2 years. The spring–summer Z_{p30} was calculated on the basis of the changes in the density of the April–May and August–September cohorts from each year. For the autumn–winter Z_{p30} , the August–September and April–May densities of the following year were taken into consideration.

The total instantaneous mortality rate was computed using the confined individuals (Z_b) as

$$Z_b = -\ln(N_t / N_o)$$

where N_o is the number of individuals placed in cages and N_t is the number of surviving clams at the time specimens being replenished. Z_b was fitted to the monthly rate (Z_{b30}) in the same way as (Z_{p30}).

During the 2007–2008 fishing campaign (from October to March), ARouSA was used to calculate the instantaneous fishing mortality rate (F), transforming the daily catches in weight by size class into catch in number (C) by applying a size–weight regression so that

$$F = -\ln(C / N_o)$$

where N_o is the number of specimens in the stock assessment from the month of September prior to the start of the campaign [26]. Catch data were collected daily from a floating platform (Figure 1), where all vessels were required to stop at the end of the fishing day. To obtain the size structure of the catches, 625 individuals from the catches of 25 randomly chosen vessels were measured every 15 days.

2.3. Relationship between variables and mortality modeling

To determine the seasonality of the environmental variables and the growth and mortality rates of the confined specimens, the seasonal coefficient from each month (SC_i), defined as

$$SC_i = m_i - M$$

was used, where m_i is the mean of the variable in month i of all the years included in the time series and M is the mean of the variable in the whole series. A comparison of means of the variables with a normal distribution (Shapiro–Wilk test) was carried out by means of the t test. The medians of the variables that were not normal were compared by means of the Mann–Whitney U test.

To determine the existence of density-dependent factors, the stock–recruitment (S – R) relationship was fitted to Shepherd’s model:

$$R = aS / \left[1 + (S/K)^b \right]$$

where a is the slope at the origin, b is the extent to which the density-dependent components compensate for the changes in stock size, and K is the stock threshold above which the density-dependent components predominate over the density-independent ones [21]. The fit was carried out minimizing the residual sum of squares. By means of a Person’s correlation analysis, we also examined the relationship between the log survival rate ($\log(R/S)$ [27]) and (i) density, (ii) the biomass of *P. aureus*, and (iii) the density, and (iv) biomass of all the commercial infaunal bivalves.

A study of the relationship between the presence–absence (P – A) of recruitment in the August–September samplings and the rest of the variables was carried out by means of log regressions, assigning a value of 1 to the dependent variable when recruitment was found and 0 in the opposite case. The log regression expression used was

$$\ln \left[p / (1 - p) \right] = a + bX$$

where a and b are constants, X is the independent variable, and p is the probability that recruitment will appear in the August–September sampling according to X . The regression was fitted for maximum probability, using an iterative process to find the values of a and b that minimized the expression

$$L(\beta) = \sum \left\{ y_i \ln(p(x_i)) + [1 - y_i] \ln(1 - p(x_i)) \right\}$$

where $p(x_i)$ corresponds to

$$p = e^{a+bX} / (1 + e^{a+bX})$$

Significance was evaluated using statistic G

$$G = 2 * \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n \left[y_i \ln(p(x_i)) + (1 - y_i) \ln(1 - p(x_i)) \right] - \left[n_1 \ln(n_1) + n_0 \ln(n_0) + n \ln(n) \right] \right\}$$

where n_1 and n_0 are the number of observations of y with values 1 and 0, and n is the total number of observations. In these cases, G follows the chi-square distribution with 1 degree of freedom [28].

Mortality was modeled using a backward regression analysis in which the dependent variable was Zb_{30} , and the independent variables were T , S , F , and CF . The variables were previously LOESS smoothed [29] using the correlogram of each variable as the smoothing parameter. The correlograms were calculated with the statistical pack PAST. To make sure that no multicollinearity existed, the following points were verified: (i) the correlations between the variables were <0.8 , (ii) the sum of the coefficients of determination of the simple regressions with each independent variable was less than the coefficient of determination of the multiple regression, and (iii) the variance inflation factor (VIF) was <10 [30].

3. Results

3.1. Environmental variables

Temperature (T) fluctuated between 11.3°C and 19°C , salinity (S) ranged between 25.2 and 35.8, and fluorescence (F) ranged from 1.2 to $14.9 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ Chl a. The values of T and S were high from June to November and low from December to April, whereas F exhibited two cycles with high values (March–June and August–October) (Figure 2). Seasonality was confirmed by the autocorrelograms (Supplementary Figure 1). T and S showed recurring values with a lag of 11–12 months, and F with a lag of five to six months (Supplementary Figure 1). The mean T value in spring–summer (16.3°C) was higher than that of autumn–winter (14.1°C) ($t = 5.354, p < 0.001$). The mean S was 34.59 in spring–summer and 33.12 in autumn–winter. The median was higher in spring–summer than in autumn–winter ($U = 302, p = 0.001$). The mean F was 5.04 and $3.84 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ Chl a in spring–summer and autumn–winter, respectively; the median was higher in spring–summer than in autumn–winter ($U = 356, p = 0.011$).

Figure 2 • Seasonal coefficient (SC) of the temperature (T), salinity (S), and fluorescence (F) from February 2006 to December 2011. Source of raw data: INTECMAR.

3.2. Density, mortality, and growth

The density of *P. aureus* ranged from 8.55 and 62.29 ind m^{-2} and showed a downward but fluctuating trend with a “sawtooth” pattern from the beginning of the study until the minimum value was reached in April 2009. In September 2009, its density increased to its initial values but decreased again with highs and lows until reaching a new minimum in April 2011. Biomass ranged between 23.66 and 76.30 g m^{-2} with changes paralleling that of density. The density of the group of commercial infaunal bivalves (including *P. aureus*) fluctuated between 46.02 and $118.66 \text{ ind m}^{-2}$ with minimum values also being found in April 2009 and 2011. Biomass ranged from 314 to 551 g m^{-2} exhibiting minimum values in August 2006 and April 2009 (Figure 3). In 2006 and in September 2007–2010, *P. aureus* accounted for over 45% of the density of commercial infaunal bivalves (Supplementary Table 1). Despite the progression of the “sawtooth” pattern, no significant differences were found between the spring–summer and autumn–winter density modes ($U = 9; p = 0.174$) or between the biomass modes during these same periods ($U = 11; p = 0.297$). Neither the density nor the biomass of the group of infaunal bivalves exhibited significantly differentiated modes between spring–summer and autumn–winter ($U = 10; p = 0.230$ and $U = 15; p > 0.689$).

Figure 3 • Variation in density (ind m^{-2} , panel a) and biomass (g m^{-2} , panel b) of *P. aureus* (black symbols) and of all the commercial infaunal bivalves (panels a and c; white symbols) over the 2006–2011 period.

Three size classes were identified in the size frequencies of the stock assessments (Supplementary Table 1). In years 2006, 2007 and 2011, two annual recruitments were detected (in April–May and August–September) which produced two cohorts per age class. In 2008, 2009, and 2010, no specific August–September cohort of recruits was found. In April 2009, some small-sized dispersed individuals appeared sporadically, but their number was not sufficient to identify a cohort of recruits with the methods used (Supplementary Figure 2).

The cohorts recruited in April–May were assigned to age classes 0, 1, or 2 years with mean sizes of 7.46–11.4, 17.51–23.62, and 26.63–32.66 mm, respectively. The recruit cohorts from August to September were assigned to age classes 0, 1, and 2 years with mean sizes of 7.42–11.76, 15.23, and 25.68 mm, respectively (Supplementary Table 1).

The size–weight regressions corresponding to the stock assessments and to the confined specimens are shown in **Supplementary Table 2**. Condition factor (CF) fluctuated between 0.8 and 1.3, exhibiting high values in June–August and December–January and low values in February and November (**Figure 4**). The mean CF value in spring–summer (1.05) was greater than that of autumn–winter (0.97) with highly significant differences ($t = 3.4407$; $p = 0.001$). The seasonal coefficient and the autocorrelogram (**Supplementary Figure 3**) suggest a pattern that could be fitted to a cycle of either 6 or 12 months.

Figure 4 • Seasonal coefficient (SC) of the condition factor (CF), growth rate G30 with the scale incremented 10 times ($G_{30} \times 10$), and mortality rate (Zb30) of the specimens placed in cages.

The growth equation obtained from the modal progression of the population implies that growth is greater than that in the confinement cages (**Supplementary Table 3**) and it comes closer to the size ranges found for the age classes of the cohorts recruited in April (**Figure 5**). This equation indicates that sizes of 13.17 and 22.35 mm are reached at the end of the first and second years of life. In the equation resulting from confined specimens, the seasonal nature of growth is practically non-existent ($C = 0.016$), and the function bears a greater resemblance to the age–size relationship of the September recruitments. At the end of the first and second years of life, they reached 12.05 and 20.46 mm. The bias-corrected bootstrap 95% confidence interval of growth in the confinement cages overlaps with both the growth curve of the modal progression and the size ranges of the different size classes. The confidence interval boundaries are 7.69 and 16.20 mm at the end of the first year of life and 14.22 and 26.33 mm at the end of the second year of life. G30 had values ranging from 0.001 to 0.029, and the seasonal coefficient showed high values without any significant differences between each other in the months of March and September (**Figure 4**). This biannual seasonality was confirmed by the autocorrelogram (**Supplementary Figure 3**). Moreover, the means corresponding to March and September were significantly different from those observed in any of the other months (**Table 1**).

The mean instantaneous monthly mortality rate (Zp30) was 0.20 (equivalent to a finite rate of 18%) during the first year (ages classes 0–1 year) and 0.15 (14%) in the second year, but the differences between the modes of the two sets of values were not significant. Within the 1–2 years age classes, the mean Zp30 was 0.94 (61%) in spring–summer and 0.14 (13%) in autumn–winter and the modes of the two periods differed significantly ($p = 0.027$). In autumn–winter 2007–2008, the Zp30 of the specimens over one year of age was 0.16, whereas the instantaneous fishing mortality rate was 0.003. With the exception of February 2011 when the instantaneous monthly mortality rate in boxes (Zb30) (1.08) was considered to be an outlier, this variable showed

values ranging between 0 and 0.35. The variable exhibited a very pronounced yearly variation with maximum seasonal coefficient values found in July (**Figure 4**), and its corresponding autocorrelogram showed cycles lasting 11–12 months (**Supplementary Figure 3**). Like Zp30, Zb30 was significantly higher in spring–summer (mean 0.17) than in autumn–winter (mean 0.1) ($U = 403$; $p = 0.004$).

Table 1 • Student t values for a comparison of the monthly mean values of G30.

	Jan	Mar	May	Jul	Sep	Nov
Mar	5.3442	--	5.157	3.578	0.48137	5.7573
p	<0.001	--	<0.001	<0.001	0.6311	<0.001
Sep	4.8916	0.48137	4.6924	3.4143	--	5.1576
p	<0.001	0.6311	<0.001	<0.001	--	<0.001

p , probability of similarity of the monthly mean values. Significant differences are shown in bold type.

Figure 5 • Growth curves obtained from the modal progression in the shellfish bed (Bed) and from the growth of the caged specimens (Boxes). CI Boxes, bias-corrected bootstrap confidence interval of the caged specimens. Apr range and Sept range, size ranges of the age–size relationship of the cohorts recruited in April and September, respectively.

3.3. Relationships between environmental and biological variables

The stock–recruitment relationship was fitted to Shepherd’s model ($SSR = 648.61$; $n = 9$; coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.673$) with $K = 39.003 \text{ ind m}^{-2}$ (**Figure 6a**). The log survival rate had a significant negative correlation with the density ($r^2 = -0.831$, $p < 0.01$) and biomass ($r^2 = -0.731$, $p < 0.05$) of *P. aureus* and with the density of all the commercial infaunal bivalves ($r^2 = -0.714$, $p < 0.05$) (**Figure 6b**).

The absence of a cohort of recruits in September 2008, 2009, and 2010 was fitted to a log regression where the independent variables used were minimum T and F in June and July ($G = 8.32$; $p = 0.004$ in both cases), so that with a minimum $T < 15.2^\circ\text{C}$ or minimum $F > 1.7 \mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ Chl a in June and July, the probability that no cohort of recruits would be found in September was greater than 0.96 and 0.92, respectively. It was not possible to relate by log regression either the CF or the mortality rates (Zp30 and Zb30) in spring–summer to the absence of a recruitment in September 2008, 2009, and 2010, but G30 ($G = 25.5$; $p < 0.001$) proved to be related. With mean G30 values >0.0072 in July, the probability that a specific cohort of recruits would not be identified in September was greater than 0.99 (**Supplementary Figure 4**).

Figure 6 • Density-dependent relationships: (a) fit of the stock–recruitment (S–R) relationship to Shepherd’s model. (b) Relationship of the log survival rate with density (closed dots and continuous line) and with the density of commercial infaunal bivalves (triangles and dashed dotted line). The lines are the linear regressions with coefficients of determination $R^2 = 0.691$, 0.534 , and 0.509 for the density and biomass of *P. aureus* and the density of bivalves, respectively.

CF showed a significant positive correlation with T ($r^2 = 0.264$; $p = 0.031$), but not with either S or F . G30 exhibited a significant positive correlation with F ($r^2 = 0.341$; $p = 0.049$), but not with either T or S . A significant negative correlation was found between G30 and CF ($r^2 = -0.372$; $p = 0.036$). Zp30 did not correlate either with (i) the density or (ii) biomass of *P. aureus* or with (iii) the density or (iv) biomass of the group of commercial infaunal bivalves. Nor was any significant correlation found with CF. Moreover, within the cohorts aged 1–2 years, no significant correlation was found with either size or age. Zb30 correlated significantly with T ($r^2 = 0.391$; $p = 0.0015$) and with CF ($r^2 = 0.325$; $p = 0.009$). Zb30 had a significant negative correlation with S ($r^2 = -0.386$; $p = 0.035$) in autumn–winter, whereas in spring–summer, it did not correlate with any of the variables. On the basis of the resulting autocorrelograms, a LOESS smoothing procedure, factor 12, was applied to the series of data corresponding to T , S , and Zb30, while factor 6 was applied to the F data series. Two smoothed series of data were generated for CF, one with a smoothing factor of 6 (CF - LOESS6) and the other with a factor of 12 (CF-LOESS12) (Supplementary Figure 5). After the values were smoothed, Zb30 showed a very significant correlation with T ($r^2 = 0.382$; $p = 0.001$) and a highly significant correlation with F ($r^2 = 0.463$; $p < 0.001$). A high significant correlation was found with CF, but it was higher with CF-LOESS12 ($r^2 = 0.568$; $p < 0.001$) than with CF-LOESS6 ($r^2 = 0.533$; $p < 0.001$). When Zp30 was log transformed ($\log(x + 1)$) to fit the range to that of Zb30, the correlation between the two was significant ($r^2 = 0.632$; $p = 0.049$) resulting in a significant regression ($F = 5.34$; $p = 0.049$) as well, which showed that Zb30 explains 32.5% of the variance of Zp30 (Figure 7).

Figure 7 • Monthly instantaneous mortality rate in the confinement cages (Zb30) LOESS smoothed, mortality rate of the population (Zp30), and estimated rates for the regression models for the whole study period (Z^*), for autumn–winter ($Z^* \text{ A-W}$), and for spring–summer ($Z^* \text{ S-S}$).

T , S , F , and CF explained 71.7% of the variance of Zb30 from 2006 to 2011 ($F = 42.737$; $p < 0.001$) and 90.1% in autumn–winter ($F = 71.56$; $p < 0.001$). In spring–summer, 53.4% of the variance of Zb30 was explained by T , S , and CF ($F = 13.96$; $p < 0.001$). None of the three regression models presented any evidence of multicollinearity or redundancy between the independent variables (Supplementary Table 4). It was the spring–summer 2007 period that showed the greatest discrepancy between the expected mortality rate and the one that was observed. During this period, the maximum rate observed was 0.06 units greater than the rate expected from the regression models for the whole period and for spring–summer (Figure 7).

4. Discussion

Despite being of secondary commercial importance, *P. aureus* accounted for 55% of the density and 20% of the biomass of commercial bivalves. The mean values of density (8.55–62.29 ind m^{-2}) and biomass (23.66–76.30 g m^{-2}) over the course of six years were higher than those found in other areas where the species is also harvested. During the periods of the greatest abundance in the Bay of Arcachon (France), the mean density and biomass reached 1.104 ind m^{-2} [6] and 4.28 g m^{-2} [8]. No significant correlation was found between the Zp30 of *P. aureus* and the density or biomass of this species or of the groups of commercial infaunal bivalves. However, the downward trend in density and biomass (Figure 3) could be explained by the density-dependent stock–recruitment relationship (Figure 6). In fact, the critical threshold of the density of parent stock ($K = 39.003$ ind m^{-2}) was exceeded in four of the twelve samplings: in May and August 2006, August 2007, and September 2009 (Supplementary Table 1). In the case of clams confined in the boxes, their density (125 ind m^{-2}) was well below this threshold. The negative influence of the density-dependent factors on the abundance of the populations has been studied extensively [12, 27].

The presence of a variable number of recruit cohorts in the same year is not unusual, and this pattern is generally related to the marine climate [14]. Variable patterns have been described for *V. corrugata*, *V. decussata*, and *V. philippinarum* consisting of only one peak or a main peak and one or more secondary peaks between spring and autumn [31–33]. In the case of *P. aureus*, Gallois [10] described a spawning episode from May to July and

another from September to November in the French Mediterranean. In Galicia, Álvarez Fariña [11] found that the spawning of July and autumn of a specific year took place earlier, and in spring and summer, the following year. The interannual variability in the number and duration of the spawning periods is closely related to environmental conditions [34, 35]. Gallois [10] reported that total gonadal regression did not occur in *P. aureus*, so that given the appropriate environmental conditions, it would be possible to have two or more spawnings. Álvarez Fariña [11] pointed out that the gametogenesis of this species depends highly on environmental factors since these animals have a small amount of reserve tissue which does not provide enough energy for the sustenance of the final stages. Moura et al. [36] also found a strong influence between the reproductive cycle of *P. aureus* and fluctuations in both seawater temperature and chlorophyll a.

The positive relationship between the presence of a second cohort of recruits in September and temperature in June and July (**Supplementary Figure 4**) is in keeping with the dependence of the recruitments on environmental conditions. The negative relationship between the presence of a recruitment in September and the fluorescence may be consistent based on two assumptions: (i) Despite the fact that the minimum values of fluorescence were lower in June and July in the years in which a September recruitment was detected, the availability of food may not have been a limiting factor. In this case, temperature may be the decisive factor in the presence–absence of recruitments in September [37, 38]. Riva and Massé [39] consider the optimum temperature for spawning in *P. aureus* to be between 15°C and 20°C. This range is consistent with the threshold of a minimum temperature of 15.2°C in June and July estimated in this study for the presence of a September recruitment (**Supplementary Figure 4**). Beukema and Dekker [40] suggest that successful recruitment of *Mytilus edulis* Linnaeus, 1758 could be relatively independent of food availability. Moreover, fluorescence may not reflect the entire availability of food since particulate organic matter also comprises a large part of the diet of this species [41]. (ii) The cohort of recruits in September 2008, 2009, and 2010 may be hidden owing to an overlap with a recruitment in April that continued for a longer period of time. In fact, the size variance in September of the cohorts recruited in April is greater during these years than in others (**Supplementary Table 1**) and the log regression between the variance of these sizes and the presence–absence of recruitment in September was significant. A lower growth rate coinciding with an extended recruitment period during the summer could favor this overlap. Therefore, the negative relationship between G30 and the detection of a September recruitment also proved to be consistent with this hypothesis (**Supplementary Figure 4**).

The size–weight relationship measured for *P. aureus* in the Bay of Arcachon [7] predicts 16% larger weights for the same-sized individuals compared with our model. This difference may be due to the seasonal variation of the size–weight relationship since those from Arcachon were calculated in June and July, whereas those from O Bohído, with the exception of caged specimens (period Feb-06–Nov-11), were calculated in April–May and September–October. In fact, the seasonal coefficient of CF was greater in June and August (**Figure 4**). High values in condition indices based on weight are usually associated with periods of gonadal maturity [42], while low values tend to correspond to spawning periods [43], which would explain the positive correlation of CF with temperature and its negative correlation with

G30. The fact that CF shows a seasonality of both 6 and 12 months is in keeping with the variability of the reproductive cycle of this species. The lack of significance in the log regression between the CF of the previous months and the presence–absence of the September recruitments corroborates the theory that the absence of recruitment in September 2008, 2009, and 2010 could be more due to the overlap of the April recruitment than due to an actual non-existent recruitment in September.

The maximum sizes of 39.94 and 43.55 mm from the different VBGF-E in this study were similar to those of 30–40 mm reported in Arcachon [7], 44.7 mm in the Adriatic Sea (Italy) [44], and 37 mm in Egypt [41]. The parameters of the VBGF for this species in the Adriatic Sea were $L_{\infty} = 44.7$ mm, $K = 0.44$ y⁻¹, and $t_0 = 0.37$ [44]. This implies that the size range would be 15.88–26.14 mm at the end of the first and second year of life. These sizes are larger than those obtained in this study based on data from the population (13.17 and 22.35 mm) and confined specimens (12.05 and 20.46 mm). However, they are included within the bias-corrected bootstrap 95% confidence intervals (7.69–16.20 and 14.22–26.33 mm).

The VBGF-E models show that the growth observed in the box-confined clams was representative of the population in the bed. However, it must be considered that all the confined specimens were over 1 year of age, and therefore, the growth estimates tend to be lower if specimens of all the different ages were used. The growth of the cohorts recruited in September was lower than that of the April recruits and G30 correlated significantly with fluorescence, but not salinity or temperature. Similarly, Brown [37] found that the Chl b concentration sometimes had a greater effect than temperature on the growth of the oyster *Magallana gigas* (Thunberg, 1793). Thus, greater food availability could favor April recruits over those of September, which would explain these differences in growth (**Figure 5**). The biannual seasonality of G30 suggests that growth would probably have a better fit with a seasonal model that included two season points (one in summer and one in winter) than with a model having only one point as the VBGF-E used here. This is probably why factor C of the two growth functions obtained is so different, to the extent that the function obtained in the confinement cages is practically non-seasonal.

The fishing mortality rate shows that harvesting has very little impact on the population. Although the fishery administration has established a minimum catch size of 20 mm, the peculiar nature of the non-targeted species causes it to be caught with fishing gear aimed at species with a higher minimum catch size. Therefore, the effective minimum catch size of *P. aureus* is actually 30 mm (unpublished data taken from catch size monitoring programs). This effective catch size corresponds to the modal size of age classes over 2 years old, and therefore, only a small percentage of the population is affected by the fishery. Consequently, it can be concluded that most of the Zp30 is due to natural causes. Zb30 was lower than Zp30 for specimens from 1 to 2 years of age, likely owing to the net covering on the cages which prevented predators from entering. Since the temporal variation of Zb30 is very similar to that of Zp30 (**Figure 7**), it is possible to say that the effect of predators was not very important in the temporal variability of natural mortality.

The mortality rates during the first year of life in spring–summer in specimens between 1 and 2 years of age may be considered high [45], whereas the rates recorded during the second year of life or during the autumn–winter period were moderate. In bivalve

mollusk populations, mortality rates are usually higher during the first year of life and tend to decrease as the animals get older [46]. In addition to temperature and salinity, CF proved to be important in modeling Zb30 (**Supplementary Table 4**). Since CF is associated with gametogenesis between spawning periods, the increase in mortality rates among specimens between 1 and 2 years of age during the spring–summer period may be associated with the reproductive cycle. The independent variables used explained the high percentages of variability in mortality rates (71.67% during the whole period and 90.1% in autumn–winter). However, the variability explained by these variables dropped to 53.35% when considering the spring–summer mortality. Since the confined specimens were protected from predators, only the pathological aspects of the population, which were not examined in this study, could be considered as possible variables to add to these models for an improved fit. Similarly, Carballal et al. [47] described a high prevalence of a neoplastic disease in specimens from this bed, which may be related to their mortality.

The relationships between environmental variables such as temperature, salinity, and food availability with the growth and mortality of this species are complex and highlight the vulnerability of bivalve mollusks and the economy associated with their exploitation to changes in environmental conditions. The results of this study are of great value for proposing fishery management measures for this species according to their biology and for assessing their effectiveness by distinguishing the influence of environmental variations. It also highlights the importance of adapting management measures to climate change.

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Author contributions

The authors declare that all authors contributed equally, approve this work, and take full responsibility.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

Data supporting these findings are available within the article or upon request.

Institutional review board statement

Not applicable.

Informed consent statement

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